

Methodological Approaches In Grammar Description of Sign Languages

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Overview (Part I)

Notion of grammar

Grammar Description

Data Collection Methods

Documentary vs. corpus linguistics

Language Documentation

Overview (Part II)

Comparative review of methods with LD

Language Documentation as approach: text, lexicon, grammar

Requirements: Language Resources

Data ownership, governance, stewardship

Case study: Hungary and Estonia

GRAMMAR

- **grammar as system**
- **grammar as competence**
- **grammar as performance**
- **grammar as rules**
- **grammar textbook**

GRAMMAR DESCRIPTION

Different types of grammar description

Mosel (2006)

- (1) the preliminary grammar that presents the very first account of a language's structure on the basis of a small corpus;**
- (2) the introductory grammar chapter that accompanies the treatise of a specific research topic;**
- (3) the summary of a large reference grammar;**
- (4) the grammar in the front matter of a dictionary;**
- (5) the sketch grammar of a language documentation**

Pfau, Steinbach & Woll (2015)

Branchini & Mantovan (2020)

Makaroglu, Dikyuva, Arik (2017)

Klomp (2021)

**Der Konditionalsatz in Deutscher Gebärdensprache (DGS)
und Brasilianischer Gebärdensprache (Libras)
- Eine empirische soziolinguistische Studie**

Dissertation

zur Erlangung des philosophischen Doktorgrades
an der Philosophischen Fakultät der Georg-August-Universität Göttingen

vorgelegt von
Liona Paulus
aus Ochsenfurt

Göttingen, 2021

**Relative Clause Constructions in Turkish Sign
Language**

**Dissertation
zur Erlangung des Grades des Doktors der Philosophie
Fachbereiche Sprache, Literatur, Medien I & II
der Universität Hamburg**

vorgelegt von

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aus Ankara**

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**ESHARANI GRAMMATICAL SKETCH:
AN INITIAL DESCRIPTION OF THE LEXICON AND GRAMMAR**

ARDAVAN GUILTY

A DISSERTATION

Submitted to the Department of Linguistics
and the Graduate School of Gallaudet University
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Grammar design and structure

The Linguistics of British Sign Language

An Introduction

Rachel Sutton-Spence and Bencie Woll

Example 1: Sutton-Spence & Woll (1999).

Wh- questions

These request new information from a wide range of possibilities. They are called 'Wh- questions' because in English all Wh- questions contain a question word that begins with *wh-* (*what, why, where, when, who, which, and how* (in the past *how* also began with *wh-*)). Unlike Yes-No questions, in BSL these questions do have a special question sign. Examples of Wh- questions include *Where did you go for your holiday? When does this programme finish? Who is that man? Why are you late?* None of these questions can reasonably be answered by a simple *yes* or *no*.

French also has similar 'qu- questions' including the words *qui, quelle, quoi, quand, comment, and combien* (although *où* does not fit in). In BSL there is less similarity between these question signs, although many do have some sort of repeated movement (WHAT, WHAT-FOR, WHO, WHICH, and WHERE have a side-to-side movement and WHEN, HOW-MANY, HOW-MUCH, HOW-OLD have an internal movement). WHY and HOW fit less well into this pattern, although they are also question signs.

Facial expression is also important in Wh- questions. The general rule for Wh- questions is that the brows are furrowed (abbreviated as 'bf'), the eyes are slightly closed, and the head is thrust slightly forward or slightly tilted to one side.

Again, though, this is just a general rule. As we said earlier with Yes-No questions, puzzlement or anger can lead to lowered eyebrows. If the person asking the question is surprised or just showing polite interest, then even though the question has a Wh- sign, the eyebrows are raised.

The British linguist Margaret Deuchar has said that the facial expression is not so much a distinction between Wh- and Yes-No questions, as between ones which request a lot of information and those which do not.

The brows are furrowed to show a puzzled face for Wh-, but only if the questioner genuinely does not know the answer. A mother talking to a toddler may ask 'Where's Teddy?' in order to get the child to point at a picture. In this case her eyebrows are raised and not furrowed. This is in contrast to a genuine question where the mother does not know where the child put the teddy (fig. 4.1):

_____bf
TEDDY WHERE
'Where's Teddy?' (questioner does not know the answer)

_____br
TEDDY WHERE
'Where's Teddy?' (question with known answer)

Raised eyebrows are also used in BSL to signal turn-taking. This means that signers raise their brows when they are ready to hand the signing turn to the other person. For this reason, a Wh- question may end with raised brows.

Fig. 4.1a Wh- question with unknown answer WHERE?

Fig. 4.1b Wh- question with known answer WHERE?

Sign order is also relevant here. We said earlier in chapter 3 that in BSL, the question signs most often come at the end of the sentence. Sometimes the Wh- sign comes both at the beginning and at the end of the sentence, as for example, in WHERE CAT WHERE. This can be analysed as a sort of 'question copy', like 'pronoun copy'. It may also occur for emphasis.

The sign glossed as WHAT and another question sign made with palms turned upwards are often used as general question markers and as general markers for turn-taking. These are always placed at the end of the sentence.

Alternative questions (or Which-questions).

These questions only allow for an answer already provided in the question. For example, If Mary asks *Would you like tea, coffee or milk?* she allows Jane only the possibility of answering *tea, coffee, or milk*. She does not expect *orange squash* and also does not expect the answer *Yes*. In BSL these questions are mainly distinguished from Yes-No questions by the optional use of the question sign WHICH at the end: LIKE TEA COFFEE MILK WHICH.

Note: it is possible to use the sign WHICH in a Wh- question as well. For example, TODAY SANDWICHES, WHICH FILLING? is an ordinary Wh- question because no choice is given in the sentence. TODAY SANDWICHES HAM, CHEESE, PEANUT-BUTTER WHICH? is a 'Which' or 'Alternative' question because the choices are given in the sentence.

Rhetorical questions

We have said that questions ask for information, but there are also times when this is not their function. Rhetorical questions are one type of question that

Bound morphemes

A morpheme is considered to be the smallest unit of meaning in a language. Morphemes can be free, meaning they can stand alone (such as English words, e.g., “house”, “fine”, or “no”), or bound, which means they must be connected to another morpheme (such as English suffixes, e.g., “-ed”, “-s”, etc.). To code for bound morphemes, ID glosses will be provided for their meaning and they will be enclosed in curly brackets. One example of where bound morphemes can be found in signed languages is in numeral incorporation, in which the quantifiable unit is usually represented by phonological aspects like placement, movement and orientation and the numeral is represented by the handshape. For example, in LSH, “two gourdes” can be represented by moving the hand as if producing the sign for GOURDE but with the handshape from the sign TWO (see figure 13).

GOURDE

TWO

Example 2:

Hochgesang & McAuliff (2016).

FINISH itself is a morpheme that can be used with other morphemes to create larger units of meaning (phrases and sentences). Figure 26 shows FINISH in combination with other signs creating a short sentence.

LSH: BIRD SIT FINISH

Translation: The bird sat.

Figure 26. LSH sentence with FINISH

In short, duality of patterning is the ability to combine a set of meaningless units (which is a limited set of forms) into a nearly infinite set of meaningful units (words and sentences). LSH exhibits this feature, thought to be one of the most critical design features of human languages.

Based on the brief discussion above, we can clearly see that LSH exhibits the design features that are critical for distinguishing a natural human language from an animal communication system or an artificially created language.

1.1 Objetivos da gramática

Gramática da Libras

Org. Ronice Müller de Quadros

UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SANTA CATARINA

CNPq Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico

1X 00:00:00 / 00:00:56

CC

Capítulo 1 - Apresentação da Gramática da Libras

1.1 Objetivos da gramática

1.2 O que é uma gramática

1.3 Os tipos de gramática

1.4 O tipo de gramática que estam...

1.5 O Corpus de Libras: os Surdos...

1.6 Os dados da Libras apresenta...

1.7 Os estudos gramaticais da Lib...

1.8 Organização desta gramática

Capítulo 2 - Introdução sobre a Língua Brasileira de Sinais: língua, cultura, história, política

Capítulo 3 - Sinais

Capítulo 4 - Sentenças

Capítulo 5 - Texto

Capítulo 6 - Pesquisas realizadas sobre a Libras: Resumos de teses e dissertações

Example 3:

Quadros et al. (2024).

What is a „good“ reference grammar?

Noonan (2006), Rice (2007)

accessibility and user-friendliness

descriptive adequacy (descriptive depth)

exemplification

comprehensiveness

addendum: unimodal

Usability of language data

reliability

verifiability

generalizability

reproducibility

linguistic knowledge

language knowledge

How to make sure that description
based on reliable data?

**How can we verify
what we describe
as a grammar feature?**

Exemplification:

plurality

Fig. 6.1: Plural marking with the body anchored noun WOMAN in DGS. Copyright © 2005 by Buske Verlag. Reprinted with permission.

Fig. 6.3: Plural marking with the midsagittal noun BOOK in DGS. Copyright © 2005 by Buske Verlag. Reprinted with permission.

VERB MORPHOLOGY

There is information about number in verbs, too. BSL verbs give information about whether an action is performed more than once, or if more than one person is involved in the action. In the verb I-TEACH-THEM-ALL, the sweeping movement of the verb TEACH indicates that a group receives the single action of a single person. In the verb I-TEACH-EACH-OF-THEM, the repeated and distributive movement indicates that a number of individuals each receives the single action of a single person (fig. 6.8). This contrasts with the absence of distributive movement in I-TEACH-HIM. It should be noted that repetition of movement in a verb can have different meanings depending on the rest of the sentence. Repetition of GO, for example, without distributed movement can mean either that one individual goes repeatedly, or that many individuals go. In chapter 8 we will discuss in more depth the information provided by verbs in BSL.

Plural

One of the values of the category number, indicating that there is more than one of an entity.

Table Morphology-3: The potential full paradigm of verbal inflection for person and number in LSE. The table shows the various possible combinations of verbal inflection for first/non-first person and singular/plural categories for typical agreeing verbs. Where both subject and object are non-first person, they are not co-referential. 1P = first person; XP = non-first person; SG = singular; PL = plural (multiple)

			OBJECT			
			1P		XP	
			SG	PL	SG	PL
SUBJECT	1P	SG				
		PL				
	XP	SG	5	6	7	8
		PL	9	10	11	12

(136) AJUDAR(recíproco)

(137) CONVERSAR EM LIBRAS (recíproco)

(139) Verbo DIMITIR com movimentos reduplicados, distribuídos em arco, marcando uma leitura exaustiva.

(138) MANDAR MENSAGEM (recíproco)

**Also, how collect we data?
And why?**

Rationale beyond data collection

- (a) Natural language data...**
- (b) ... of language knowledge...**
- (c) ... from diverse language settings**
- (d) ... provided by signers**
- (e) ... to describe grammar features**

Methods

Corpus-based

Elicitation-based

Experiment-based

Checklist-based

Consultation-based

design

focus

strengths vs. weaknesses

What is the definition of corpus?

McEnery & Wilson (2001)

- (a) collection of texts**
- (b) machine-readable**
- (c) real-world language use**
- (d) representative**
- (e) finite**

What is a documentation-based corpus?

Woodbury (2003) => **documentary linguistics**

(a) annotated

(b) diverse in discourse (settings, genre, style, register, etc)

(c) large (limit?)

(d) ongoing, distributed, opportunistic

(e) preservable and portable

(f) ethical

Language documentation

Himmelman (1998), Woodbury (2003), Austin

lasting, multi-purpose record (Himmelman, 1998)

ongoing, expanding, organistic (Woodbury, 2003)

annotated data (McEneaney, 2001)

language resources and toolkit (Good

data management: F.A.I.R and Austin principles

data governance: C.A.R.E principles

Relevance of language documentation in grammar description

- (1) countermeasuring language endangerment**
- (2) accessing to the own language**
- (3) mobilizing deaf language and linguistic knowledge**

**DOCUMENTATION OF
TEXT, LEXICON, GRAMMAR**

**What do we need to describe a grammar of
sign language**

in sign language?

Do you want to know? :)